

Motionless balls in a spherical shell

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1 The frictionless case

We want to occupy ourselves with the balance of two balls on a spherical shell. We have the following questions: Is this balance stable, unstable, or indifferent? What position do the two balls have? Which quantities determine the balance?

Two balls with mass m_1, m_2 and radii R_1, R_2 are on a spherical shell with the radius R_K , see fig.

We don't take friction into consideration. At first, we assume a vacuum. The problem is in determining the angles γ_1, γ_2 .

$$\gamma_1 = \angle FMS_1 \quad \gamma_2 = \angle FMS_2$$

Then, the force on an inclined plane with the angle of inclination β is:

$$F = mg \sin \beta$$

see fig.

m = moved mass g = earth's acceleration

On the spherical shell the forces are:

$$F_1 = m_1 g \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_2 = m_2 g \sin \gamma_2$$

Here γ_1, γ_2 are the angles of inclination, see fig.

The spherical shell is balanced, thus $F_1 = F_2$. Equating, we get:

$$m_1 \cdot \sin \gamma_1 = m_2 \cdot \sin \gamma_2$$

We view the fig.

We need the cosine law to determine γ_g :

$$(R_1 + R_2)^2 = (R_K - R_1)^2 + (R_K - R_2)^2 - 2 \cdot (R_K - R_1) \cdot (R_K - R_2) \cdot \cos \gamma_g$$

transformed:

$$\cos \gamma_g = \frac{(R_K - R_1)^2 + (R_K - R_2)^2 - (R_1 + R_2)^2}{2 \cdot (R_K - R_1) \cdot (R_K - R_2)}$$

In this way, γ_g is known:

$$\gamma_g = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 \quad (1)$$

$$m_1 \cdot \sin \gamma_1 = m_2 \cdot \sin \gamma_2 \quad (2)$$

(1) can be inserted with the addition theorem $\sin(a-b) = \sin a \cos b - \sin b \cos a$.

$$m_1 \sin \gamma_1 = m_2 \sin(\gamma_g - \gamma_1) = m_2 \cdot (\sin \gamma_g \cos \gamma_1 - \sin \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_g)$$

Insertion of $\cos \gamma_1 = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \gamma_1}$ and transformation:

$$m_1 \sin \gamma_1 + m_2 \sin \gamma_1 \cos \gamma_g = m_2 \sin \gamma_g \cdot \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \gamma_1}$$

squared:

$$\sin^2 \gamma_1 \cdot (m_1 + m_2 \cos \gamma_g)^2 = m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g - m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g \sin^2 \gamma_1$$

solved for $\sin \gamma_1$:

$$\sin \gamma_1 = \sqrt{\frac{m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g}{(m_1 + m_2 \cos \gamma_g)^2 + m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g}} = \frac{m_2 \sin \gamma_g}{\sqrt{(m_1 + m_2 \cos \gamma_g)^2 + m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g}}$$

and $\gamma_2 = \gamma_g - \gamma_1$

with medium:

φ_F = density of the liquid (gas)
 φ_{Ki} = density of the ball i $i \in \{1, 2\}$
 $a_i := 1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_{Ki}}$
(see Budo [2] §16 p.85)

In a medium (liquid or gas), the forces can be represented as:

$$F_1 = a_1 g m_1 \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_2 = a_2 g m_2 \sin \gamma_2$$

The equations (1) and (2) change to ($F_1 = F_2$):

$$a_1 m_1 \sin \gamma_1 = a_2 m_2 \sin \gamma_2$$

$$\gamma_g = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$$

We set $M_i := a_i \cdot m_i$ with $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and, thus, we transform in the same way as in a vacuum. We obtain:

$$\sin \gamma_1 = \frac{a_2 m_2 \sin \gamma_g}{\sqrt{(a_1 m_1 + a_2 m_2 \cos \gamma_g)^2 + a_2^2 m_2^2 \sin^2 \gamma_g}}$$

and $\gamma_2 = \gamma_g - \gamma_1$

In the frictionless case both balls have a stable balance.

2 Motionless balls on a spherical shell with friction

Now we view the friction case. We will see that there is a free play because of the friction forces - in contrast to the frictionless case.

The notation is the same as in section 1.

m_1, m_2 = mass of the balls
 R_1, R_2 = radii of the balls
 R_K = radius of the spherical shell

It is valid as in the frictionless case, see section 1:

$$\cos \gamma_g = \frac{(R_K - R_2)^2 + (R_K - R_1)^2 - (R_1 + R_2)^2}{2 \cdot (R_K - R_2) \cdot (R_K - R_1)} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_g = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 \quad (4)$$

In the friction case, there is free play because of friction forces F_{R1} and F_{R2} .

F_{R1}, F_{R2} = friction case of the balls with the radii R_1 and R_2 .

Here γ_1, γ_2 are pitch angles of the balls as in section 1. The forces can be written as:

$$F_1 = \delta_1 m_1 g \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_2 = \delta_2 m_2 g \sin \gamma_2 \quad (5)$$

$$F_{R1} = m_1 g \cos \gamma_1 \cdot \mu_1 \quad F_{R2} = m_2 g \cos \gamma_2 \cdot \mu_2$$

with $i \in \{1, 2\}$

$$\delta_i := \begin{cases} \frac{5}{7} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} < \mu_{Hi} \text{ (rolling)} \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} < \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \frac{5}{7} \text{ or } 1 & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} = \mu_{Hi} \neq 0 \text{ (decision remains open)} \\ 1 & \text{if } 0 = \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} = \mu_{Hi} \text{ (frictionless)} \end{cases}$$

see Assmann [1] edition 1 chapter 11.10 p. 265

μ'_i = rolling friction coefficient of the ball i with radius R_i
 μ_{Hi} = static friction coefficient of the ball i

μ_{Gi} = sliding friction coefficient of the ball i

and

$$\mu_i = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} > \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (rolling)} \\ \mu_{Gi} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} > \mu_{Hi} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \mu_{Gi} \text{ or } \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} & \text{if } \mu_{Hi} = \frac{\mu'_i}{R_i} \text{ (decision remains open)} \end{cases}$$

see Assmann [1] edition 1 chapter 11.10 p.265

The acceleration b on the inclined plane is:

$b = \delta g \cdot \sin \alpha$, the velocity v and the distance s are $v = \delta g \sin \alpha \cdot t$ and $s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta g \cdot t^2 \cdot \sin \alpha$.

If a ball is rolling on the inclined plane, it is $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$ i.e. Budo [2] §57 p.302 Gl. (8). The moment of inertia J of a ball is $J = \frac{2}{5} \cdot mR^2$. The general formula for rolling on the inclined plane can be written:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}} \quad (6)$$

One derivation can be found at * at the end of the text or we can see this with Budo [2] §57 p.302 Gl. (5)-(7). The ball's moment of inertia insertion leads to:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{2}{5} \cdot m} = \frac{5}{7} \cdot g \sin \alpha \quad (7)$$

Then we have, in the case of rolling, $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$.

stability inequality: $|\cdot| = \text{value in } R$

$$|F_1 - F_2| \leq F_{R1} + F_{R2}$$

limit cases:

$$F_1 - F_2 = F_{R1} + F_{R2} \quad F_2 - F_1 = F_{R1} + F_{R2} \quad (8)$$

With (3) we can determine γ_g and then with (4),(5),(6) and lastly γ_1 and γ_2 that are searched. We get subintervals of $[0, 90^\circ]$ for γ_1 and γ_2 .

In a medium with the factors:

$$a_i = 1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\varphi_{Ki}} \quad \text{see Budo [2] §16 p.85}$$

with

φ_{Ki} = density of the ball i with radius R_i $i \in \{1, 2\}$
 φ_F = density of the medium (liquid, gas)

only equation (5) changes to:

$$F_1 = \delta_1 m_1 a_1 g \sin \gamma_1 \quad F_{R1} = m_1 a_1 g \cos \gamma_1 \cdot \mu_1$$

$$F_2 = \delta_2 m_2 a_2 g \sin \gamma_2 \quad F_{R2} = m_2 a_2 g \cos \gamma_2 \cdot \mu_2$$

The equations (3),(4) and (6) remain unchanged. The calculation is the same.

Both balls are in stable balance in a determined area. If we move the balls out of the area, then the balls move to their previous position. However, in this determined area, both balls can be shifted arbitrary. That means an indifferent balance in this determined area.

to *: The derivation of formula (6):

Notations:

$$\text{kinetic energy} = E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

$$\text{potential energy} = E_{pot} = mgh \text{ with } h = h_s \sin \alpha \text{ see fig.}$$

$$\text{rotational energy} = E_{rot} = \frac{Jw^2}{2} \quad J = \text{moment of inertia}$$

law of conservation of energy:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jw^2}{2} = mgh$$

We assume that the body is only rolling not gliding. Then it is valid:

$$\text{angular velocity} = w = \frac{v}{R} \quad R = \text{radius of the rolling body}$$

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jv^2}{2R^2} = mgh_s \sin \alpha$$

With transformation we yield:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}}$$

Because the rolling body has the constant acceleration $b = g \sin \alpha$, there is a uniform accelerated motion. For this motion it is valid: $v^2 = 2h_s \cdot b$ transformed to $b = \frac{v^2}{2h_s}$. Now we insert the equation of v :

$$b = \frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{2h_s \cdot (m + \frac{J}{R^2})} = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}$$

Then we have the wanted formula.

References

- [1] Bruno Assmann "Technische Mechanik" Band 1 Oldenbourg Verlag 12.edition Munich 1991
- [2] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980